

Extension of the homogenized Belgian historical climate series Monthly minimum and maximum temperatures

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1 Introduction

Instrumental meteorological observations in Belgium began in the 18th century. An inventory of the first observations can be found in Quetelet (1834) and Demarée et al. (2002). The deployment of a climatological network with regular observations of temperature and precipitation at various locations across the country dates back to the 1870s. These observation records are extremely valuable for studying the climate evolution. However, climatological time series are often affected by non-climatic factors (WMO, 2020). The location and the environment of the measurement site, the instrumentation itself as well as the observation practices may change during the measurement period. In addition, most series are composite. It means that several station records at nearby locations are concatenated to produce the final series. Each concatenation introduces an homogeneity break in the time series. In Belgium, the progressive replacement of open shelters by Stevenson closed shelters in the early 1950s is also a source of inhomogeneities in the historical series (Delvaux et al., 2019). These non-climatic factors affecting the meteorological records reduce the reliability of the time series for assessing actual climate variations. In order to evaluate climate trends, the homogenization of the long-term climate series is therefore required. This homogenization process aims at removing the non-climatic signal in these time series.

The homogenization of the historical temperature data from the climatological network of the Royal Meteorological Institute of Belgium is extensively described in Delvaux et al. (2019). The monthly means of the minimum and maximum daily air temperature at 1.5 m height above ground have been homogenized using the HOMER software (Mestre et al., 2013). The results were provided for 61 series over the period 1954–2015 (long series) and for 16 series starting before 1931 (historical series) including eight covering the full time period 1880–2015. The dataset presented here is the extension of the 16 longest series to 2023.

2 Method

The HOMER homogenization tool is a semi-automatic software which combines features from statistical methods, including PRODIGE (Caussinus and Mestre, 2004), ACMANT (Domonkos et al., 2011), and cghseg a joint segmentation method that was developed originally by biostatisticians in the context of DNA segmentation (Picard et al., 2011). These methods detect breakpoints by optimizing the segmentation of the time series into homogeneous subseries, using a dynamic programming approach to minimize internal variance (Caussinus and Lyazrhi, 1997). A break is first identified at a given year and, in second step, the method seeks to refine the break position by identifying the month. Based on the identified breakpoints, these methods apply a network-wide unified correction model (ANOVA, Caussinus and Mestre (2004)). It is worth pointing out that HOMER adjusts the data preceding a detected breakpoint to make them homogeneous with the data after that breakpoint. In this way, the most recent data (i.e., following the most recent breakpoint) are not modified. This offers a clear advantage for ongoing monitoring in that new data can be simply appended to the time series. Note that the break correction is different for each month in order to take into account the seasonal dependence of some factors of inhomogeneities. For example, a new building in the vicinity of a station may produce a shadowing effect in the winter but not in the summer.

For this new homogenization phase, non-homogenized monthly data after 2015 are first appended to the homogenized series available until 2015. The original data are the daily minimum and maximum temperatures, respectively referred hereafter as TN and TX. Monthly means are derived from valid daily values with a minimum threshold of 90 % available daily values within a month. If this criterion is not met, the monthly value is considered as missing. During the homogenization phase,

new inhomogeneity breaks may appear in the extension period (after 2015) but also in the previously homogenized period. Indeed, appending new data could reveal additional breaks, which were not identified during the previous homogenization phase, particularly near the end of previously homogenized series (i.e., 2015). Fig. 1 shows an example of a break identified in 2014 by pairwise detection of PRODIGE in the TX series of Botrange/Mont-Rigi. Each plot represents the difference between the annual temperatures of the Mont-Rigi series (candidate series) with those of the neighbouring series. The value of σ which appears on each plot is the minimum detectable amplitude (MDA), which indicates the largest amplitude of the non-detected breaks. A low MDA indicates a high correlation between the candidate and the neighbouring series. The pairs are displayed in ascending order of MDA. A clear discontinuity appears in almost all pairs in 2014, which is the signature of break in the candidate series.

Merging between historical and corresponding long series

It must be noticed that the homogenizations of the historical and long series have been performed separately in Delvaux et al. (2019). As a result, the positions and the amplitudes of the homogeneity breaks are not exactly the same in the historical series and the corresponding long series. The homogenization process of the historical series is based on a limited number of series which were all regrouped in one cluster extending over the whole country. In contrast, the number of long series was large enough to regroup them in 5 clusters with similar climatological conditions. Therefore, it is expected that the positions and the amplitudes of the breaks in the long series are more reliable. As shown in Vrábek et al. (2017), the minimum detectable amplitude of break-points is generally smaller for the long series than for the historical series which confirms that the availability of close neighbours allows a better identification of the break points in the long series. In the present homogenization phase, we produce only one series merging the homogenized long series for the period where it is available with the historical series for the period preceding the start of the long series. This approach is followed for all series except when the metadata clearly support the choice of the corrections applied in the historical series against those applied in the long series.

3 Extension of the historical series to 2023

Among the 16 historical series, 11 were extended and homogenized until december 2023. Two measurement stations were closed: Maredsous (code 220) in 2013 and Ezemaal (code 206) in 2017. The Rochefort series is interrupted in december 2018. Observations are available again in Rochefort since september 2021. Filling the gap and extending this series will be performed in a next phase. The homogenization of two series, namely Oostende (code 212) and Deurne (code 201), is currently limited to 2020 due to data quality issues. Table 1 lists the available series, their location, altitude together with their start and end dates. The location of the last segment of the series is given as well. The location of the series is also displayed on Fig. 2

A detailed description of the series and the results of the extension are described in appendices A to P. For each series, the different stations composing the different segments are listed. The breaks already identified in the historical series after the previous homogenization phase are included in the list. The breaks identified in the corresponding long series starting in 1954 are also given. The availability of new data for extending the series is also given in the appendices and, for each series, the original and homogenized minimum (TN) and maximum (TX) series are plotted.

The new homogenization process has been performed using all available long series in order to increase the number of available neighbours for identifying homogeneity breaks. Foreign series used in the previous homogenization phase were included as well. With respect to the previous phase,

Table 1: List of homogenized series with latitude and longitude (decimal degrees), altitude (m), start and end dates.

CODE.LS	NAME	LAT	LON	ALT	DATE_BEGIN	DATE_END
201	DEURNE	51.1922	4.4531	14	1880-02	2020-12
203	ZAVENTEM	50.8972	4.5281	58	1889-01	2023-12
206	EZEMAAL	50.7708	5.0011	47	1913-07	2016-12
208	JALHAY	50.5958	5.9050	290	1880-01	2023-12
210	LEUVEN	50.9044	4.6628	32	1930-05	2023-12
212	OOSTENDE	51.1992	2.8528	5	1880-01	2020-12
213	SINT-TRUIDEN	50.7722	5.1614	84	1880-01	2023-12
216	LEOPOLDSBURG	51.0697	5.2797	39	1881-01	2023-12
217	ROCHEFORT	50.1761	5.2244	193	1892-06	2018-12
218	CHIMAY	49.9819	4.3403	318	1910-09	2023-12
219	STAVELLOT	50.3978	5.9356	320	1890-02	2023-12
220	MAREDSOUS	50.3481	4.7358	240	1893-01	2013-11
221	GEMBLoux	50.5825	4.6908	157	1881-05	2023-12
222	MONT-RIGI	50.5117	6.0747	673	1928-01	2023-12
223	THIMISTER	50.6981	6.0347	220	1881-02	2023-12
224	UCCLE	50.7975	4.3592	100	1880-01	2023-12

some modifications have been brought to the grouping in 5 clusters in order to guarantee that all historical series are surrounded by sufficient neighbouring series. The series Deurne 201 has been homogenized using a new cluster centred on Antwerp. Cluster 3 has been extended to provide more neighbours for the historical series located in Brussels, in the Flemish Brabant and in the Walloon Brabant. Cluster 5 (south of Belgium) does not include any historical series and it has been merged with cluster 4 to increase the number of available series for the homogenization of the historical series located in Cluster 4. Note that the Homer identification of the breaks in a given series is performed by comparison with the most correlated series in the same cluster. When extending a cluster, an additional series which is only poorly correlated with the candidate historical series will have a very limited impact on the breaks identification of this historical series. Different clustering have been tested and the impact on the homogenisation appears very limited.

Six additional breaks have been introduced with respect to those already identified in the previous homogenization phase. As explained earlier, the historical series and the corresponding long series are merged using the historical series before 1954 and the corresponding long series after. It means the final homogenized series are produced from the raw non-homogenized series by applying the break corrections of the long series after 1954 and the break corrections of the historical series before. For some series, the names of the historical and corresponding long series are different and a choice has been made. Consequently, the names in the present report may differ from those in the extended homogenization report (Vrábel et al., 2017). The codes of the merged series are those of the historical series.

The final lists of all homogeneity breaks in TN and TX series are given in Tables 2 and 3, respectively. Next to the dates and amplitudes of the breaks, these tables also give the minimum detectable amplitude. When clearly identified, the origin of the breaks is also mentioned. Many breaks are caused by instrumental changes or by upgrades of the shelter type from open to closed. The evolution of the network was progressive and generally not well documented. The precise dates of the changes are unknown and, as a result, the origin of many breaks cannot be clearly determined (Delvaux et al., 2019). Some additional information on the series and their homogenization can be found in Appendix Q. Fig. 3 shows the homogenized TX and TX series. Their anomalies with respect to the reference period 1961-1990 are given in Fig. 4.

Table 2: Date, amplitude, minimum detectable amplitude (MDA) and origin of the TN series breaks.
The new breaks are labelled with a * after the name.

LS code	LS name	Date	Amplitude in °C	MDA in °C	Origin
201	DEURNE *	10/2002	-0.25	0.14	
201	DEURNE *	4/1994	0.33	0.14	
201	DEURNE	12/1950	-1.29	0.17	observer change
201	DEURNE	1/1931	0.60	0.17	station catenation
203	ZAVENTEM	12/2005	-0.28	0.15	
203	ZAVENTEM	12/1980	-0.26	0.15	relocation
203	ZAVENTEM	12/1953	-0.81	0.16	station catenation
203	ZAVENTEM	12/1911	-0.31	0.16	
206	EZEMAAL	12/1996	0.19	0.13	observer change
206	EZEMAAL	12/1971	0.29	0.13	
206	EZEMAAL	2/1959	-0.75	0.13	
206	EZEMAAL	12/1949	0.29	0.17	
208	JALHAY	3/1996	1.02	0.15	station catenation
208	JALHAY	12/1983	-0.42	0.15	
208	JALHAY	12/1971	0.97	0.15	
208	JALHAY	12/1950	-0.52	0.22	observer change
208	JALHAY	12/1916	0.23	0.22	
210	LEUVEN	12/1984	0.30	0.13	station catenation
210	LEUVEN	12/1972	0.37	0.13	
210	LEUVEN	12/1953	0.86	0.16	
210	LEUVEN	12/1945	-0.89	0.16	
210	LEUVEN	12/1938	1.37	0.16	
210	LEUVEN	12/1933	-0.74	0.16	
212	OOSTENDE	12/2006	-0.42	0.14	
212	OOSTENDE	12/1991	0.48	0.14	
212	OOSTENDE	12/1988	-0.52	0.14	
212	OOSTENDE	12/1970	-0.32	0.14	
212	OOSTENDE	4/1940	-0.36	0.17	station catenation
212	OOSTENDE	12/1919	-0.26	0.17	
213	SINT-TRUIDEN	12/1983	0.69	0.13	
213	SINT-TRUIDEN	12/1970	-0.19	0.13	
213	SINT-TRUIDEN	12/1944	0.73	0.19	
213	SINT-TRUIDEN	6/1938	-1.88	0.19	station catenation
213	SINT-TRUIDEN	12/1892	0.36	0.19	
216	LEOPOLDSBURG	12/1981	-0.32	0.15	station catenation
216	LEOPOLDSBURG	5/1940	-0.20	0.19	
216	LEOPOLDSBURG	12/1914	0.55	0.19	
217	ROCHEFORT	12/2008	-0.52	0.17	
217	ROCHEFORT	12/1991	0.60	0.17	
217	ROCHEFORT	12/1966	-0.45	0.17	
218	CHIMAY	12/1947	-0.66	0.17	
218	CHIMAY	12/1927	0.32	0.17	
218	CHIMAY	12/1919	0.58	0.17	
219	STAVELOT *	3/2018	-0.33	0.20	
219	STAVELOT	12/1984	-0.58	0.17	relocation
219	STAVELOT	12/1965	0.58	0.17	
219	STAVELOT	12/1959	0.66	0.17	
219	STAVELOT	12/1938	-0.32	0.20	
219	STAVELOT	12/1919	-0.39	0.20	
220	MAREDSOUS	12/1949	0.37	0.18	
220	MAREDSOUS	12/1936	-0.42	0.18	
221	GEMBLOUX	12/1980	-0.24	0.17	
221	GEMBLOUX	12/1943	0.71	0.20	
221	GEMBLOUX	12/1941	-0.98	0.20	
221	GEMBLOUX	12/1915	0.28	0.20	
222	MONT-RIGI	12/1960	-0.19	0.12	
222	MONT-RIGI	12/1937	-0.33	0.17	
223	THIMISTER	12/2004	-0.66	0.19	station catenation
223	THIMISTER	12/1971	-0.64	0.19	
223	THIMISTER	12/1968	0.66	0.19	
223	THIMISTER	12/1945	0.35	0.22	
223	THIMISTER	12/1934	0.58	0.22	
223	THIMISTER	12/1921	-1.01	0.22	
223	THIMISTER	12/1899	0.48	0.22	station catenation
224	UCCLE	6/1983	0.15	0.17	station catenation
224	UCCLE	6/1886	-0.59	0.17	station catenation

Figure 1: Example of break identification by HOMER pairwise detection.

Figure 2: Historical climates series in Belgium (Courtesy of Thomas Muller, Belgian Climate Centre).

Figure 3: Homogenized annual minimum and maximum temperature series

Figure 4: Homogenized annual minimum and maximum temperature anomalies with respect to the reference period 1961-1990.

Table 3: Date, amplitude, minimum detectable amplitude (MDA) and origin of the TX series breaks. The new breaks are labelled with a * after the name.

LS code	LS name	Date	Amplitude in °C	MDA in °C	Origin
201	DEURNE	12/1950	-1.29	0.17	observer change
201	DEURNE	1/1931	0.60	0.17	station catenation
203	ZAVENTEM	12/2005	-0.20	0.11	
203	ZAVENTEM	12/1980	-0.25	0.11	relocation
203	ZAVENTEM	12/1953	-2.12	0.18	station catenation
203	ZAVENTEM	12/1940	0.39	0.18	
203	ZAVENTEM	12/1932	-0.64	0.18	
203	ZAVENTEM	12/1908	0.94	0.18	
206	EZEMAAL	12/1988	-0.26	0.09	
206	EZEMAAL	12/1978	0.29	0.09	
206	EZEMAAL	8/1954	-1.49	0.15	station catenation
208	JALHAY *	10/2015	0.64	0.16	
208	JALHAY	12/1970	-0.40	0.17	
208	JALHAY	12/1950	-0.72	0.23	observer change
208	JALHAY	12/1925	-0.68	0.23	
208	JALHAY	12/1887	0.62	0.23	
210	LEUVEN	12/1999	-0.27	0.09	
210	LEUVEN	12/1962	-0.24	0.09	
212	OOSTENDE	12/2006	-0.28	0.16	
212	OOSTENDE	4/1940	-0.96	0.20	station catenation
212	OOSTENDE	2/1936	0.27	0.20	station catenation
213	SINT-TRUIDEN	1/2008	-0.44	0.10	relocation
213	SINT-TRUIDEN	12/2001	-0.34	0.10	
213	SINT-TRUIDEN	12/1971	0.33	0.10	
213	SINT-TRUIDEN	12/1953	-0.55	0.17	station catenation
213	SINT-TRUIDEN	12/1915	0.57	0.17	
213	SINT-TRUIDEN	12/1913	-1.15	0.17	
216	LEOPOLDSBURG	12/2001	0.13	0.11	
216	LEOPOLDSBURG	12/1973	-0.24	0.11	
216	LEOPOLDSBURG	5/1940	-0.51	0.16	
217	ROCHEFORT	no breaks		0.11	
217	ROCHEFORT	12/1950	-0.60	0.15	observer change
217	ROCHEFORT	12/1927	-1.24	0.15	
217	ROCHEFORT	12/1919	0.61	0.15	
218	CHIMAY	12/1963	-0.34	0.13	
218	CHIMAY	12/1945	-0.45	0.16	
218	CHIMAY	12/1931	-0.91	0.16	
218	CHIMAY	12/1913	0.94	0.16	
219	STAVELOT	12/1959	0.67	0.13	
219	STAVELOT	12/1939	-1.64	0.15	
219	STAVELOT	12/1936	0.76	0.15	
219	STAVELOT	12/1917	-0.36	0.15	
219	STAVELOT	12/1908	-0.23	0.15	
220	MAREDSOUS	10/1991	-0.51	0.09	station catenation
220	MAREDSOUS	12/1966	0.26	0.09	
220	MAREDSOUS	12/1942	-0.57	0.16	
220	MAREDSOUS	12/1923	-0.38	0.16	
221	GEMBLOUX	12/2011	-0.24	0.10	
221	GEMBLOUX	12/1943	-0.77	0.15	
221	GEMBLOUX	12/1916	-0.43	0.15	
221	GEMBLOUX	12/1895	0.46	0.15	
221	GEMBLOUX	12/1890	-0.82	0.15	
222	MONT-RIGI *	11/2014	-0.45	0.12	
222	MONT-RIGI	7/1989	0.57	0.16	station catenation
222	MONT-RIGI	11/1984	0.52	0.16	station catenation
222	MONT-RIGI	12/1977	-0.38	0.16	
222	MONT-RIGI	11/1953	-1.23	0.15	station catenation
222	MONT-RIGI	12/1935	0.49	0.15	
223	THIMISTER *	11/2013	0.38	0.14	
223	THIMISTER	12/2004	0.55	0.12	station catenation
223	THIMISTER	3/1989	-0.58	0.12	relocation
223	THIMISTER	12/1975	0.37	0.12	
223	THIMISTER	12/1956	-0.46	0.12	
223	THIMISTER	12/1947	-0.68	0.19	
223	THIMISTER	12/1936	-0.79	0.19	
223	THIMISTER	12/1932	-0.71	0.19	
223	THIMISTER	12/1927	0.28	0.19	
223	THIMISTER	12/1923	1.57	0.19	
224	UCCLE	6/1983	-0.91	0.15	station catenation
224	UCCLE	12/1899	0.51	0.15	
224	UCCLE	12/1890	-0.51	0.15	

4 Series analysis

A basic analysis of the homogenized series is presented in this section. First, we compare the averaged TN and TX temperatures for successive 30-year periods ending in 2020. The first period extends from 1881 to 1900 and includes only 20 years. The evolution of these averages are shown for each series in Fig. 5. The average for a given series and a given period is not displayed if more than 20 % of the yearly values are missing. Yearly values can be missing in the first periods when the series starts later than 1881 and in the last period when the series is interrupted before 2023. For series where both 1881-1900 and 1991-2020 averages are available, the difference between these two periods ranges from 1.4 to 1.8 °C for TN and from 1.7 to 2.1 °C for TX. The average of the daily mean temperature (TM), estimated as the arithmetic mean of TN and TX, ranges from 1.6 to 1.9 °C. The mean differences between the two periods are 1.6, 1.8 and 2.0 °C for TN, TM and TX, respectively.

As already apparent in Fig. 3 and 4, the temperature rise is clearly not linear over the whole time period. This is particularly true for TX where an overall negative trend is observed during a period extending approximately from the late 40s to the early 80's. Fig. 6 shows the anomalies with respect to the reference period 1961-1990. For TX, a decrease is observed between the 1931-1960 and the 1961-1990 periods while a slight increase is observed for TN. Between 1961-1990 and 1991 and 2020, a warming close to 1 °C is obtained for TN while the increase in TX exceeds 1.2 °C for most series.

The temperature trends within the period 1981-2023 have been evaluated using a linear least-square regression. The trends, expressed in °C/10-year, are shown in Fig. 7 for TN and TX. The trends for the mean temperature TM are given as well. The trends in TN, TM and TX exceed 0.3, 0.4 and 0.5 °C/10-year, respectively, for all series except MAREDSOUS (CODE 220). The MAREDSOUS series is only available until 2013 which results in lower trends. The p-value is substantially lower than 0.01 for all series except for MAREDSOUS. Excluding MAREDSOUS, the mean trends for all available series are 0.35, 0.45 and 0.56 °C/10-year for TN, TM and TX, respectively. Note that the trends obtained from the non-homogenized series are 0.34, 0.44 and 0.53 °C/10-year, respectively. The trends and the p values for non-homogenized and homogenized TN, TX and TM series are given in appendix R. Differences between non-homogenized and homogenized series trends are due to breaks identified after 1981 but also to missing data in the non-homogenized series which have been replaced by estimated values by the homogenization tool.

Seven series extend over the full 1881-2023 period. These series have been averaged to produce mean series of TN, TM and TX (Fig. 8). These series give an overall view over the temperature trends. However, the 7 series are not homogeneously distributed over the Belgian territory and the average cannot be considered as representative of the mean Belgian climate. The temperature anomalies with respect to the reference period (1961-1990) are shown in Fig. 9.

5 Data and metadata files

The produced dataset has been made available on the RMI open data portal with the support of the Belgian Climate Centre. A zip file can be downloaded under the product name "Homogenized monthly climates series".

The datafiles can be found in the /DATA/CSV and /DATA/TXT directories and in 2 different formats:

- ho_monthly_series_<code>_<var>_<version>.<ext>, where <code> is the series code, <var> is the variable name, respectively tx and tn for maximum and minimum temperatures, <version> is the version (v2024_01), and <ext> is either csv or txt. Each row contains the 12 monthly values of TN or TX for a given year.
- ho_monthly_series_<code>_tn_tx_<version>.<ext>, where <code> is the series code, <version> is the version (v2024_01), and <ext> is either csv or txt. Each row contains both TN and TX values for a given month.

The metadata files can be found in the /METADATA directory. It contains:

- series_metadata_<version>.csv, corresponding to the Table 1 above, the list of all series with code, name, latitude, longitude, altitude, start date and end date. Latitude and longitude are given in decimal degrees. Altitude (above mean sea level) is given in m.
- series_breaks_tx_<version>.csv and series_breaks_tn_<version>.csv, corresponding to resp. Table 2 and 3 below, the lists of all detected breaks in TX and TN series, respectively.

Documentation can be found in /INFO:

- homogenized_tt_series_users_guide_v2024_01.pdf, the present user's guide.
- series_history_breaks_<version>.pdf, a document containing for each series its history and the detected breaks.

Figure 5: Evolution of the minimum and maximum temperature averages from the homogenized series.

Figure 6: Evolution of the minimum and maximum temperature anomalies with respect to the reference period 1961-1990 from the homogenized series.

Figure 7: Linear trends for the minimum (TN), mean (TM) and maximum (TX) temperatures for the period 1981-2023 from the homogenized series.

Figure 8: Homogenized annual minimum, maximum and mean temperature series averaged over the 7 series extending over the full 1881-2023 period. Thick lines represent 10-year moving averages.

Figure 9: Homogenized annual minimum, maximum and mean temperature anomalies (Ref. period : 1961-1990) averaged over the 7 series extending over the full 1881-2023 period. Thick lines represent 10-year moving averages.

6 Summary and perspectives

This report presents the extension of 16 homogenized historical temperatures series starting before 1931, including eight starting in 1880. These series represent the climatic variations of the monthly means of the daily minimum and maximum temperatures. Among these series, 11 were extended until 2023. The homogenization was performed using the HOMER software as described in Delvaux et al. (2019) and 6 new homogeneity breaks have been identified and corrected. The corresponding long series (starting in 1954) and historical series (starting before 1931) which were distinct in the previously homogenized dataset have been here merged. The extended series, the metadata and a user manual have been made available on the RMI open data portal with the support of the Belgian Climate Centre.

A short analysis of the homogenized series has been performed. It shows that the temporal evolutions of TN and TX are not synchronous and that the warming is more pronounced for TX than for TN. The temperature difference between 1881-1900 and 1991-2020 ranges from 1.4 to 1.8 for TN and from 1.7 to 2.1 for TX. The average over all available series are 1.6 and 2.0 for TN and TX, respectively. The mean linear trend for the period 1981-2023 are 0.35 and 0.56 °C/10-year for TN and TX, respectively.

The present extension is a first step of a wider work on the homogenization of climate series. First, we will investigate how to extend the 5 historical temperature series which have not been extended here due to a lack of observational data. The extension of the 45 temperature series starting in 1954 and homogenized until 2015 will be addressed as well. The homogenization of monthly precipitation is also a very important task which has been already conducted at RMI. In Bertrand et al. (2021), homogenization results are provided for 110 series over the period 1951–2019 and for 18 series starting before 1912 including nine covering the full time period 1880–2019. These series need to be extended as well. So far, only monthly time series have been homogenized. Homogenization of temperature and precipitation data at daily or even sub-daily timescale is still a topic of ongoing research but the production of such series is highly desired for studying the climate evolution of extremes. Finally, next to temperature and precipitation, the homogenization of other surface climate data series like wind or solar radiation would be of great benefit for the climate community.

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ANNEX - Series history and breaks

A DEURNE 201

A.1 History and homogenization of the series until 2015

A.1.1 History until 2015

HISTORICAL SERIES

201 - DEURNE (1880 – 2015)

Reference location – longitude: 4°24' 0", latitude: 51°13' 30", altitude: 10 m.

TT CODE	TT NAME	BEGIN	END	STAT ID	LON	LAT	ALT	ΔR	ΔALT
265	ANTWERPEN	2/1880	5/1914	1299	4°24' 0"	51°13' 30"	10	0.0	0
262	DOEL	6/1914	1/1931	1300	4°15' 46"	51°18' 35"	3	13.4	7
261	ANTWERPEN	2/1931	9/1950	1301	4°24' 51"	51°12' 35"	10	2.0	0
200	DEURNE	10/1950	12/2015	24	4°27' 11"	51°11' 32"	14	5.2	4

CORRESPONDING LONG SERIES

2003 - DEURNE (1954 – 2015)

Reference location – longitude: 4°27' 11", latitude: 51°11' 32", altitude: 14 m.

TT CODE	TT NAME	BEGIN	END	STAT ID	LON	LAT	ALT	ΔR	ΔALT
200	DEURNE	1/1954	12/2015	24	4°27' 11"	51°11' 32"	14	0.0	0

A.1.2 Homogeneity breaks detected until 2015

In historical series DEURNE 201:

Table 4: Detected breaks in TX historical series

LS code	LS name	Date	Amplitude in °C	MDA in °C	Metadata
201	DEURNE	9/1950	-1.00	0.26	station catenation
201	DEURNE	1/1931	-1.47	0.26	station catenation
201	DEURNE	12/1924	1.87	0.26	
201	DEURNE	5/1914	-1.63	0.26	station catenation
201	DEURNE	12/1911	1.27	0.26	

Table 5: Detected breaks in TN historical series

LS code	LS name	Date	Amplitude in °C	MDA in °C	Metadata
201	DEURNE	12/2002	-0.36	0.17	observer change station catenation
201	DEURNE	12/1997	0.45	0.17	
201	DEURNE	12/1950	-1.29	0.17	
201	DEURNE	1/1931	0.60	0.17	

In corresponding long series DEURNE 2003:

Table 6: Detected breaks in TX long series

LS code	LS name	Date	Amplitude in °C	MDA in °C	Metadata
2003	DEURNE	no breaks		0.13	

Table 7: Detected breaks in TN long series

LS code	LS name	Date	Amplitude in °C	MDA in °C	Metadata
2003	DEURNE	no breaks		0.16	

A.2 Extension of the series

A.2.1 Availability since 2015

Year	TN count	TN mean in °C	TX count	TX mean in °C
2015	12	7.17	12	15.48
2016	12	7.05	12	15.25
2017	12	7.27	12	15.58
2018	12	7.32	12	16.32
2019	12	7.16	12	15.94
2020	12	7.85	12	16.57
2021	12	6.77	12	14.76
2022	12	7.38	12	16.24
2023	12	8.05	12	15.73

A.2.2 New homogenization process

New detected breaks

Table 8: New detected breaks in TN series

LS code	LS name	Date	Amplitude in °C	MDA in °C	Metadata
201	DEURNE	10/2002	-0.25	0.14	
201	DEURNE	4/1994	0.33	0.14	

Merging between historical and corresponding long series

Table 9: Detected breaks in TX merged series

LS code	LS name	Date	Amplitude in °C	MDA in °C	Metadata
201	DEURNE	12/1950	-1.29	0.17	observer change station catenation
201	DEURNE	1/1931	0.60	0.17	

Table 10: Detected breaks in TN merged series

LS code	LS name	Date	Amplitude in °C	MDA in °C	Metadata
201	DEURNE	10/2002	-0.25	0.14	observer change station catenation
201	DEURNE	4/1994	0.33	0.14	
201	DEURNE	12/1950	-1.29	0.17	
201	DEURNE	1/1931	0.60	0.17	

Final series

Figure 10: Non-homogenized and homogenized annual minimum and maximum temperatures from 1880 to 2020

B ZAVENTEM 203

B.1 History and homogenization of the series until 2015

B.1.1 History until 2015

HISTORICAL SERIES

203 - BRUXELLES - ZAVENTEM (1889 – 2015)

Reference location – longitude: 4°21' 59", latitude: 50°51' 23", altitude: 35 m.

TT CODE	TT NAME	BEGIN	END	STAT ID	LON	LAT	ALT	ΔR	ΔALT
908	ST JOSSE TEN NODE	1/1889	12/1953	544	4°21' 59"	50°51' 23"	35	0.0	0
907	ZAVENTEM	1/1954	12/2015	171	4°31' 41"	50°53' 50"	58	12.3	23

CORRESPONDING LONG SERIES

2033 - ZAVENTEM (1954 – 2015)

Reference location – longitude: 4°31' 41", latitude: 50°53' 50", altitude: 58 m.

TT CODE	TT NAME	BEGIN	END	STAT ID	LON	LAT	ALT	ΔR	ΔALT
907	ZAVENTEM	1/1954	12/2015	171	4°31' 41"	50°53' 50"	58	0.0	0

B.1.2 Homogeneity breaks detected until 2015

In historical series BRUXELLES - ZAVENTEM 203:

Table 11: Detected breaks in TX historical series

LS code	LS name	Date	Amplitude in °C	MDA in °C	Metadata
203	BRUXELLES - ZA- VENTEM	12/2005	-0.23	0.18	
203	BRUXELLES - ZA- VENTEM	12/1980	-0.34	0.18	relocation
203	BRUXELLES - ZA- VENTEM	12/1953	-2.12	0.18	station catenation
203	BRUXELLES - ZA- VENTEM	12/1940	0.39	0.18	
203	BRUXELLES - ZA- VENTEM	12/1932	-0.64	0.18	
203	BRUXELLES - ZA- VENTEM	12/1908	0.94	0.18	

Table 12: Detected breaks in TN historical series

LS code	LS name	Date	Amplitude in °C	MDA in °C	Metadata
203	BRUXELLES - ZA-VENTEM	12/2005	-0.30	0.16	
203	BRUXELLES - ZA-VENTEM	12/1980	-0.25	0.16	relocation
203	BRUXELLES - ZA-VENTEM	12/1953	-0.81	0.16	station catenation
203	BRUXELLES - ZA-VENTEM	12/1911	-0.31	0.16	

In corresponding long series ZAVENTEM 2033:

Table 13: Detected breaks in TX long series

LS code	LS name	Date	Amplitude in °C	MDA in °C	Metadata
2033	ZAVENTEM	12/2005	-0.20	0.11	
2033	ZAVENTEM	12/1980	-0.25	0.11	relocation

Table 14: Detected breaks in TN long series

LS code	LS name	Date	Amplitude in °C	MDA in °C	Metadata
2033	ZAVENTEM	12/2005	-0.28	0.15	
2033	ZAVENTEM	12/1980	-0.26	0.15	relocation

B.2 Extension of the series

B.2.1 Availability since 2015

Year	TN count	TN mean in °C	TX count	TX mean in °C
2015	12	6.71	12	15.19
2016	12	6.85	12	14.79
2017	12	7.05	12	15.11
2018	12	7.15	12	15.94
2019	12	6.99	12	15.48
2020	12	7.47	12	16.32
2021	12	6.47	12	14.38
2022	12	7.45	12	16.48
2023	12	8.02	12	15.88

B.2.2 New homogenization process

New detected breaks

No new breaks have been detected since 2015.

Merging between historical and corresponding long series

Table 15: Detected breaks in TX merged series

LS code	LS name	Date	Amplitude in °C	MDA in °C	Metadata
203	BRUXELLES - ZA- VENTEM	12/2005	-0.20	0.11	
203	BRUXELLES - ZA- VENTEM	12/1980	-0.25	0.11	relocation
203	BRUXELLES - ZA- VENTEM	12/1953	-2.12	0.18	station catenation
203	BRUXELLES - ZA- VENTEM	12/1940	0.39	0.18	
203	BRUXELLES - ZA- VENTEM	12/1932	-0.64	0.18	
203	BRUXELLES - ZA- VENTEM	12/1908	0.94	0.18	

Table 16: Detected breaks in TN merged series

LS code	LS name	Date	Amplitude in °C	MDA in °C	Metadata
203	BRUXELLES - ZA- VENTEM	12/2005	-0.28	0.15	
203	BRUXELLES - ZA- VENTEM	12/1980	-0.26	0.15	relocation
203	BRUXELLES - ZA- VENTEM	12/1953	-0.81	0.16	station catenation
203	BRUXELLES - ZA- VENTEM	12/1911	-0.31	0.16	

Final series

Figure 11: Non-homogenized and homogenized annual minimum and maximum temperatures from 1889 to 2023

C EZEMAAL 206

C.1 History and homogenization of the series until 2015

C.1.1 History until 2015

HISTORICAL SERIES

206 - EZEMAAL (1913 – 2015)

Reference location – longitude: 5°4' 57", latitude: 50°45' 24", altitude: 50 m.

TT CODE	TT NAME	BEGIN	END	STAT ID	LON	LAT	ALT	ΔR	ΔALT
1100	EZEMAAL	6/1913	8/1954	1303	5°4' 57"	50°45' 24"	50	0.0	0
1201	EZEMAAL	9/1954	12/2015	481	5°0' 4"	50°46' 15"	47	6.0	3

CORRESPONDING LONG SERIES

2040 - EZEMAAL (1954 – 2015)

Reference location – longitude: 5°0' 4", latitude: 50°46' 15", altitude: 47 m.

TT CODE	TT NAME	BEGIN	END	STAT ID	LON	LAT	ALT	ΔR	ΔALT
1201	EZEMAAL	9/1954	12/2015	481	5°0' 4"	50°46' 15"	47	0.0	0

C.1.2 Homogeneity breaks detected until 2015

In historical series EZEMAAL 206:

Table 17: Detected breaks in TX historical series

LS code	LS name	Date	Amplitude in °C	MDA in °C	Metadata
206	EZEMAAL	8/1954	-1.49	0.15	station catenation

Table 18: Detected breaks in TN historical series

LS code	LS name	Date	Amplitude in °C	MDA in °C	Metadata
206	EZEMAAL	12/1996	0.21	0.17	observer change
206	EZEMAAL	12/1959	-0.61	0.17	
206	EZEMAAL	12/1949	0.29	0.17	

In corresponding long series EZEMAAL 2040:

Table 19: Detected breaks in TX long series

LS code	LS name	Date	Amplitude in °C	MDA in °C	Metadata
2040	EZEMAAL	12/1988	-0.26	0.09	
2040	EZEMAAL	12/1978	0.29	0.09	

Table 20: Detected breaks in TN long series

LS code	LS name	Date	Amplitude in °C	MDA in °C	Metadata
2040	EZEMAAL	12/1996	0.19	0.13	observer change
2040	EZEMAAL	12/1971	0.29	0.13	
2040	EZEMAAL	2/1959	-0.75	0.13	

C.2 Extension of the series

C.2.1 Availability since 2015

Year	TN count	TN mean in °C	TX count	TX mean in °C
2015	12	6.63	12	15.97
2016	12	6.61	12	15.58
2017	5	2.68	5	12.80
2018	0	–	0	–
2019	0	–	0	–
2020	0	–	0	–
2021	0	–	0	–
2022	0	–	0	–
2023	0	–	0	–

C.2.2 New homogenization process

New detected breaks

No new breaks have been detected since 2015.

Merging between historical and corresponding long series

Table 21: Detected breaks in TX merged series

LS code	LS name	Date	Amplitude in °C	MDA in °C	Metadata
206	EZEMAAL	12/1988	-0.26	0.09	station catenation
206	EZEMAAL	12/1978	0.29	0.09	
206	EZEMAAL	8/1954	-1.49	0.15	

Table 22: Detected breaks in TN merged series

LS code	LS name	Date	Amplitude in °C	MDA in °C	Metadata
206	EZEMAAL	12/1996	0.19	0.13	observer change
206	EZEMAAL	12/1971	0.29	0.13	
206	EZEMAAL	2/1959	-0.75	0.13	
206	EZEMAAL	12/1949	0.29	0.17	

Final series

Figure 12: Non-homogenized and homogenized annual minimum and maximum temperatures from 1913 to 2016

D JALHAY 208

D.1 History and homogenization of the series until 2015

D.1.1 History until 2015

HISTORICAL SERIES

208 - JALHAY (1880 – 2015)

Reference location – longitude: 5°58' 18", latitude: 50°35' 3", altitude: 298 m.

TT CODE	TT NAME	BEGIN	END	STAT ID	LON	LAT	ALT	ΔR	ΔALT
1605	JALHAY-GILEPPE	1/1880	3/1996	381	5°58' 18"	50°35' 3"	298	0.0	0
1498	STEMBERT	1/1998	12/2015	456	5°54' 18"	50°35' 45"	290	4.9	8

CORRESPONDING LONG SERIES

2052 - JALHAY (1954 – 2015)

Reference location – longitude: 5°58' 18", latitude: 50°35' 3", altitude: 298 m.

TT CODE	TT NAME	BEGIN	END	STAT ID	LON	LAT	ALT	ΔR	ΔALT
1605	JALHAY-GILEPPE	1/1954	3/1996	381	5°58' 18"	50°35' 3"	298	0.0	0
1498	STEMBERT	1/1998	12/2015	456	5°54' 18"	50°35' 45"	290	4.9	8

D.1.2 Homogeneity breaks detected until 2015

In historical series JALHAY 208:

Table 23: Detected breaks in TX historical series

LS code	LS name	Date	Amplitude in °C	MDA in °C	Metadata
208	JALHAY	12/1970	-0.49	0.23	observer change
208	JALHAY	12/1950	-0.72	0.23	
208	JALHAY	12/1925	-0.68	0.23	
208	JALHAY	12/1887	0.62	0.23	

Table 24: Detected breaks in TN historical series

LS code	LS name	Date	Amplitude in °C	MDA in °C	Metadata
208	JALHAY	3/1996	0.97	0.22	station catenation
208	JALHAY	12/1983	-0.45	0.22	
208	JALHAY	12/1971	0.80	0.22	observer change
208	JALHAY	12/1950	-0.52	0.22	
208	JALHAY	12/1916	0.23	0.22	

In corresponding long series JALHAY 2052:

Table 25: Detected breaks in TX long series

LS code	LS name	Date	Amplitude in °C	MDA in °C	Metadata
2052	JALHAY	12/1970	-0.40	0.17	

Table 26: Detected breaks in TN long series

LS code	LS name	Date	Amplitude in °C	MDA in °C	Metadata
2052	JALHAY	3/1996	1.02	0.15	station catenation
2052	JALHAY	12/1983	-0.42	0.15	
2052	JALHAY	12/1971	0.97	0.15	

D.2 Extension of the series

D.2.1 Availability since 2015

Year	TN count	TN mean in °C	TX count	TX mean in °C
2015	12	6.63	12	14.57
2016	12	6.73	12	14.18
2017	12	6.87	12	14.65
2018	12	7.01	12	15.88
2019	12	6.69	12	15.48
2020	12	7.12	12	16.13
2021	12	6.18	12	14.06
2022	12	7.19	12	16.40
2023	12	7.65	12	15.61

D.2.2 New homogenization process

New detected breaks

Table 27: New detected breaks in TX series

LS code	LS name	Date	Amplitude in °C	MDA in °C	Metadata
208	JALHAY	10/2015	0.64	0.16	

Merging between historical and corresponding long series

Table 28: Detected breaks in TX merged series

LS code	LS name	Date	Amplitude in °C	MDA in °C	Metadata
208	JALHAY	10/2015	0.64	0.16	observer change
208	JALHAY	12/1970	-0.40	0.17	
208	JALHAY	12/1950	-0.72	0.23	
208	JALHAY	12/1925	-0.68	0.23	
208	JALHAY	12/1887	0.62	0.23	

Table 29: Detected breaks in TN merged series

LS code	LS name	Date	Amplitude in °C	MDA in °C	Metadata
208	JALHAY	3/1996	1.02	0.15	station catenation
208	JALHAY	12/1983	-0.42	0.15	
208	JALHAY	12/1971	0.97	0.15	
208	JALHAY	12/1950	-0.52	0.22	observer change
208	JALHAY	12/1916	0.23	0.22	

Final series

Figure 13: Non-homogenized and homogenized annual minimum and maximum temperatures from 1880 to 2023

E LEUVEN 210

E.1 History and homogenization of the series until 2015

E.1.1 History until 2015

HISTORICAL SERIES

210 - LEUVEN (1930 – 2015)

Reference location – longitude: 4°41' 6", latitude: 50°51' 48", altitude: 28 m.

TT CODE	TT NAME	BEGIN	END	STAT ID	LON	LAT	ALT	ΔR	ΔALT
1002	HEVERLEE	4/1930	12/1984	178	4°41' 6"	50°51' 48"	28	0.0	0
1012	HERENT	11/1989	12/2015	193	4°39' 46"	50°54' 16"	32	4.8	4

CORRESPONDING LONG SERIES

2021 - LEUVEN (1954 – 2015)

Reference location – longitude: 4°41' 6", latitude: 50°51' 48", altitude: 28 m.

TT CODE	TT NAME	BEGIN	END	STAT ID	LON	LAT	ALT	ΔR	ΔALT
1002	HEVERLEE	1/1954	12/1984	178	4°41' 6"	50°51' 48"	28	0.0	0
1012	HERENT	11/1989	12/2015	193	4°39' 46"	50°54' 16"	32	4.8	4

E.1.2 Homogeneity breaks detected until 2015

In historical series LEUVEN 210:

The TX historical data was dropped because of weak data quality.

Table 30: Detected breaks in TN historical series

LS code	LS name	Date	Amplitude in °C	MDA in °C	Metadata
210	LEUVEN	12/1984	0.37	0.16	station catenation
210	LEUVEN	12/1953	0.86	0.16	
210	LEUVEN	12/1945	-0.89	0.16	
210	LEUVEN	12/1938	1.37	0.16	
210	LEUVEN	12/1933	-0.74	0.16	

In corresponding long series LEUVEN 2021:

Table 31: Detected breaks in TX long series

LS code	LS name	Date	Amplitude in °C	MDA in °C	Metadata
2021	LEUVEN	12/1999	-0.27	0.09	
2021	LEUVEN	12/1962	-0.24	0.09	

Table 32: Detected breaks in TN long series

LS code	LS name	Date	Amplitude in °C	MDA in °C	Metadata
2021	LEUVEN	12/1984	0.30	0.13	station catenation
2021	LEUVEN	12/1972	0.37	0.13	

E.2 Extension of the series

E.2.1 Availability since 2015

Year	TN count	TN mean in °C	TX count	TX mean in °C
2015	12	7.08	12	15.84
2016	12	7.03	12	15.35
2017	12	7.35	12	15.84
2018	12	7.43	12	16.67
2019	12	7.21	12	16.21
2020	12	7.69	12	16.97
2021	12	6.92	12	15.20
2022	12	7.76	12	17.18
2023	12	8.44	12	16.58

E.2.2 New homogenization process

New detected breaks

No new breaks have been detected since 2015.

Merging between historical and corresponding long series

Table 33: Detected breaks in TX merged series

LS code	LS name	Date	Amplitude in °C	MDA in °C	Metadata
210	LEUVEN	12/1999	-0.27	0.09	
210	LEUVEN	12/1962	-0.24	0.09	

Table 34: Detected breaks in TN merged series

LS code	LS name	Date	Amplitude in °C	MDA in °C	Metadata
210	LEUVEN	12/1984	0.30	0.13	station catenation
210	LEUVEN	12/1972	0.37	0.13	
210	LEUVEN	12/1953	0.86	0.16	
210	LEUVEN	12/1945	-0.89	0.16	
210	LEUVEN	12/1938	1.37	0.16	
210	LEUVEN	12/1933	-0.74	0.16	

Final series

Figure 14: Non-homogenized and homogenized annual minimum and maximum temperatures from 1930 to 2023

F OOSTENDE 212

F.1 History and homogenization of the series until 2015

F.1.1 History until 2015

HISTORICAL SERIES

212 - OOSTENDE (1880 – 2015)

Reference location – longitude: 2°54' 21", latitude: 51°13' 24", altitude: 5 m.

TT CODE	TT NAME	BEGIN	END	STAT ID	LON	LAT	ALT	ΔR	ΔALT
166	OOSTENDE	1/1880	11/1891	1310	2°55' 4"	51°13' 54"	4	1.2	1
165	OOSTENDE	12/1891	2/1899	1312	2°55' 49"	51°14' 11"	6	2.2	1
100	OOSTENDE	3/1899	2/1936	1309	2°54' 21"	51°13' 24"	5	0.0	0
103	OOSTENDE	3/1936	4/1940	1311	2°54' 53"	51°12' 12"	2	2.3	3
103	MIDDELKERKE	1/1956	12/2015	2	2°51' 10"	51°11' 57"	5	4.6	0

CORRESPONDING LONG SERIES

2001 - MIDDELKERKE (1956 – 2015)

Reference location – longitude: 2°51' 10", latitude: 51°11' 57", altitude: 5 m.

TT CODE	TT NAME	BEGIN	END	STAT ID	LON	LAT	ALT	ΔR	ΔALT
103	MIDDELKERKE	1/1956	12/2015	2	2°51' 10"	51°11' 57"	5	0.0	0

F.1.2 Homogeneity breaks detected until 2015

In historical series OOSTENDE 212:

Table 35: Detected breaks in TX historical series

LS code	LS name	Date	Amplitude in °C	MDA in °C	Metadata
212	OOSTENDE	12/2006	-0.39	0.20	
212	OOSTENDE	4/1940	-0.96	0.20	station catenation
212	OOSTENDE	2/1936	0.27	0.20	station catenation

Table 36: Detected breaks in TN historical series

LS code	LS name	Date	Amplitude in °C	MDA in °C	Metadata
212	OOSTENDE	12/2006	-0.45	0.17	station catenation
212	OOSTENDE	12/1991	0.53	0.17	
212	OOSTENDE	12/1988	-0.49	0.17	
212	OOSTENDE	12/1970	-0.37	0.17	
212	OOSTENDE	4/1940	-0.36	0.17	
212	OOSTENDE	12/1919	-0.26	0.17	

In corresponding long series MIDDELKERKE 2001:

Table 37: Detected breaks in TX long series

LS code	LS name	Date	Amplitude in °C	MDA in °C	Metadata
2001	MIDDELKERKE	12/2006	-0.28	0.16	

Table 38: Detected breaks in TN long series

LS code	LS name	Date	Amplitude in °C	MDA in °C	Metadata
2001	MIDDELKERKE	12/2006	-0.42	0.14	
2001	MIDDELKERKE	12/1991	0.48	0.14	
2001	MIDDELKERKE	12/1988	-0.52	0.14	
2001	MIDDELKERKE	12/1970	-0.32	0.14	

F.2 Extension of the series

F.2.1 Availability since 2015

Year	TN count	TN mean in °C	TX count	TX mean in °C
2015	12	6.85	12	14.22
2016	12	6.86	12	14.05
2017	12	7.14	12	14.41
2018	12	7.01	12	14.36
2019	12	6.84	12	14.54
2020	12	7.42	12	15.00
2021	12	6.61	12	13.49
2022	12	6.87	12	15.01
2023	12	7.63	12	14.59

F.2.2 New homogenization process

New detected breaks

No new breaks have been detected since 2015.

Merging between historical and corresponding long series

Table 39: Detected breaks in TX merged series

LS code	LS name	Date	Amplitude in °C	MDA in °C	Metadata
212	OOSTENDE	12/2006	-0.28	0.16	
212	OOSTENDE	4/1940	-0.96	0.20	station catenation
212	OOSTENDE	2/1936	0.27	0.20	station catenation

Table 40: Detected breaks in TN merged series

LS code	LS name	Date	Amplitude in °C	MDA in °C	Metadata
212	OOSTENDE	12/2006	-0.42	0.14	
212	OOSTENDE	12/1991	0.48	0.14	
212	OOSTENDE	12/1988	-0.52	0.14	
212	OOSTENDE	12/1970	-0.32	0.14	
212	OOSTENDE	4/1940	-0.36	0.17	station catenation
212	OOSTENDE	12/1919	-0.26	0.17	

Final series

Figure 15: Non-homogenized and homogenized annual minimum and maximum temperatures from 1880 to 2020

G SINT-TRUIDEN 213

G.1 History and homogenization of the series until 2015

G.1.1 History until 2015

HISTORICAL SERIES

213 - SINT-TRUIDEN (1880 – 2015)

Reference location – longitude: 5°11' 12", latitude: 50°48' 58", altitude: 54 m.

TT CODE	TT NAME	BEGIN	END	STAT ID	LON	LAT	ALT	ΔR	ΔALT
865	HASSELT	1/1880	8/1899	1331	5°20' 19"	50°55' 50"	40	16.6	14
1104	SINT-TRUIDEN	9/1899	6/1938	1314	5°11' 12"	50°48' 58"	54	0.0	0
1106	ZOUTLEEuw	10/1938	12/1953	208	5°7' 32"	50°50' 20"	33	5.0	21
1104	GORSEM	1/1954	12/2015	205	5°10' 27"	50°49' 48"	39	1.8	15

CORRESPONDING LONG SERIES

2037 - SINT-TRUIDEN (1954 – 2015)

Reference location – longitude: 5°9' 41", latitude: 50°46' 20", altitude: 84 m.

TT CODE	TT NAME	BEGIN	END	STAT ID	LON	LAT	ALT	ΔR	ΔALT
1104	GORSEM	1/1954	12/2015	205	5°10' 27"	50°49' 48"	39	6.5	45

G.1.2 Homogeneity breaks detected until 2015

In historical series SINT-TRUIDEN 213:

Table 41: Detected breaks in TX historical series

LS code	LS name	Date	Amplitude in °C	MDA in °C	Metadata
213	SINT-TRUIDEN	1/2008	-0.41	0.17	relocation
213	SINT-TRUIDEN	12/2001	-0.25	0.17	
213	SINT-TRUIDEN	12/1971	0.31	0.17	station catenation
213	SINT-TRUIDEN	12/1953	-0.55	0.17	
213	SINT-TRUIDEN	12/1915	0.57	0.17	
213	SINT-TRUIDEN	12/1913	-1.15	0.17	

Table 42: Detected breaks in TN historical series

LS code	LS name	Date	Amplitude in °C	MDA in °C	Metadata
213	SINT-TRUIDEN	12/1983	0.64	0.19	station catenation
213	SINT-TRUIDEN	12/1970	-0.30	0.19	
213	SINT-TRUIDEN	12/1944	0.73	0.19	
213	SINT-TRUIDEN	6/1938	-1.88	0.19	
213	SINT-TRUIDEN	12/1892	0.36	0.19	

In corresponding long series SINT-TRUIDEN 2037:

Table 43: Detected breaks in TX long series

LS code	LS name	Date	Amplitude in °C	MDA in °C	Metadata
2037	SINT-TRUIDEN	1/2008	-0.44	0.10	relocation
2037	SINT-TRUIDEN	12/2001	-0.34	0.10	
2037	SINT-TRUIDEN	12/1971	0.33	0.10	

Table 44: Detected breaks in TN long series

LS code	LS name	Date	Amplitude in °C	MDA in °C	Metadata
2037	SINT-TRUIDEN	12/1983	0.69	0.13	
2037	SINT-TRUIDEN	12/1970	-0.19	0.13	

G.2 Extension of the series

G.2.1 Availability since 2015

Year	TN count	TN mean in °C	TX count	TX mean in °C
2015	12	6.97	12	15.28
2016	12	6.76	12	15.07
2017	12	6.83	12	15.34
2018	12	6.67	12	16.35
2019	12	6.74	12	15.76
2020	12	7.12	12	16.35
2021	12	6.39	12	14.46
2022	12	7.09	12	16.41
2023	12	7.74	12	15.77

G.2.2 New homogenization process

New detected breaks

No new breaks have been detected since 2015.

Merging between historical and corresponding long series

Table 45: Detected breaks in TX merged series

LS code	LS name	Date	Amplitude in °C	MDA in °C	Metadata
213	SINT-TRUIDEN	1/2008	-0.44	0.10	relocation
213	SINT-TRUIDEN	12/2001	-0.34	0.10	
213	SINT-TRUIDEN	12/1971	0.33	0.10	station catenation
213	SINT-TRUIDEN	12/1953	-0.55	0.17	
213	SINT-TRUIDEN	12/1915	0.57	0.17	
213	SINT-TRUIDEN	12/1913	-1.15	0.17	

Table 46: Detected breaks in TN merged series

LS code	LS name	Date	Amplitude in °C	MDA in °C	Metadata
213	SINT-TRUIDEN	12/1983	0.69	0.13	station catenation
213	SINT-TRUIDEN	12/1970	-0.19	0.13	
213	SINT-TRUIDEN	12/1944	0.73	0.19	
213	SINT-TRUIDEN	6/1938	-1.88	0.19	
213	SINT-TRUIDEN	12/1892	0.36	0.19	

Final series

Figure 16: Non-homogenized and homogenized annual minimum and maximum temperatures from 1880 to 2023

H LEOPOLDSBURG 216

H.1 History and homogenization of the series until 2015

H.1.1 History until 2015

HISTORICAL SERIES

216 - LEOPOLDSBURG (1881 – 2015)

Reference location – longitude: 5°16' 17", latitude: 51°6' 28", altitude: 50 m.

TT CODE	TT NAME	BEGIN	END	STAT ID	LON	LAT	ALT	ΔR	ΔALT
800	LEOPOLDSBURG	1/1881	11/1953	1357	5°16' 17"	51°6' 28"	50	0.0	0
800	LEOPOLDSBURG	12/1953	12/1981	134	5°15' 45"	51°6' 25"	48	0.6	2
800	KOERSEL	1/1982	12/2015	135	5°16' 47"	51°4' 11"	39	4.3	11

CORRESPONDING LONG SERIES

2027 - LEOPOLDSBURG (1954 – 2015)

Reference location – longitude: 5°16' 47", latitude: 51°4' 11", altitude: 39 m.

TT CODE	TT NAME	BEGIN	END	STAT ID	LON	LAT	ALT	ΔR	ΔALT
800	LEOPOLDSBURG	1/1954	12/1981	134	5°15' 45"	51°6' 25"	48	4.3	9
800	KOERSEL	1/1982	12/2015	135	5°16' 47"	51°4' 11"	39	0.0	0

H.1.2 Homogeneity breaks detected until 2015

In historical series LEOPOLDSBURG 216:

Table 47: Detected breaks in TX historical series

LS code	LS name	Date	Amplitude in °C	MDA in °C	Metadata
216	LEOPOLDSBURG	12/2001	0.25	0.16	
216	LEOPOLDSBURG	12/1973	-0.26	0.16	
216	LEOPOLDSBURG	5/1940	-0.51	0.16	

Table 48: Detected breaks in TN historical series

LS code	LS name	Date	Amplitude in °C	MDA in °C	Metadata
216	LEOPOLDSBURG	12/1981	-0.50	0.19	station catenation
216	LEOPOLDSBURG	5/1940	-0.20	0.19	
216	LEOPOLDSBURG	12/1914	0.55	0.19	

In corresponding long series LEOPOLDSBURG 2027:

Table 49: Detected breaks in TX long series

LS code	LS name	Date	Amplitude in °C	MDA in °C	Metadata
2027	LEOPOLDSBURG	12/2001	0.13	0.11	
2027	LEOPOLDSBURG	12/1973	-0.24	0.11	

Table 50: Detected breaks in TN long series

LS code	LS name	Date	Amplitude in °C	MDA in °C	Metadata
2027	LEOPOLDSBURG	12/1981	-0.32	0.15	station catenation

H.2 Extension of the series

H.2.1 Availability since 2015

Year	TN count	TN mean in °C	TX count	TX mean in °C
2015	12	6.29	12	15.95
2016	12	6.28	12	15.62
2017	12	6.40	12	16.02
2018	12	6.31	12	17.02
2019	12	6.30	12	16.45
2020	12	6.80	12	17.25
2021	12	5.86	12	15.55
2022	12	6.37	12	17.21
2023	12	7.50	12	16.53

H.2.2 New homogenization process

New detected breaks

No new breaks have been detected since 2015.

Merging between historical and corresponding long series

Table 51: Detected breaks in TX merged series

LS code	LS name	Date	Amplitude in °C	MDA in °C	Metadata
216	LEOPOLDSBURG	12/2001	0.13	0.11	
216	LEOPOLDSBURG	12/1973	-0.24	0.11	
216	LEOPOLDSBURG	5/1940	-0.51	0.16	

Table 52: Detected breaks in TN merged series

LS code	LS name	Date	Amplitude in °C	MDA in °C	Metadata
216	LEOPOLDSBURG	12/1981	-0.32	0.15	station catenation
216	LEOPOLDSBURG	5/1940	-0.20	0.19	
216	LEOPOLDSBURG	12/1914	0.55	0.19	

Final series

Figure 17: Non-homogenized and homogenized annual minimum and maximum temperatures from 1881 to 2023

I ROCHEFORT 217

I.1 History and homogenization of the series until 2015

I.1.1 History until 2015

HISTORICAL SERIES

217 - ROCHEFORT (1892 – 2015)

Reference location – longitude: 5°13' 28", latitude: 50°10' 34", altitude: 193 m.

TT CODE	TT NAME	BEGIN	END	STAT ID	LON	LAT	ALT	ΔR	ΔALT
1469	CIERGNON	6/1892	10/1898	1352	5°5' 18"	50°10' 0"	150	9.8	43
1405	ROCHEFORT	7/1912	12/2015	326	5°13' 28"	50°10' 34"	193	0.0	0

CORRESPONDING LONG SERIES

2049 - ROCHEFORT (1954 – 2015)

Reference location – longitude: 5°13' 28", latitude: 50°10' 34", altitude: 193 m.

TT CODE	TT NAME	BEGIN	END	STAT ID	LON	LAT	ALT	ΔR	ΔALT
1405	ROCHEFORT	1/1954	12/2015	326	5°13' 28"	50°10' 34"	193	0.0	0

I.1.2 Homogeneity breaks detected until 2015

In historical series ROCHEFORT 217:

Table 53: Detected breaks in TX historical series

LS code	LS name	Date	Amplitude in °C	MDA in °C	Metadata
217	ROCHEFORT	12/1950	-0.60	0.15	observer change
217	ROCHEFORT	12/1927	-1.24	0.15	
217	ROCHEFORT	12/1919	0.61	0.15	

Table 54: Detected breaks in TN historical series

LS code	LS name	Date	Amplitude in °C	MDA in °C	Metadata
217	ROCHEFORT	12/2008	-0.53	0.22	
217	ROCHEFORT	12/1991	0.52	0.22	
217	ROCHEFORT	12/1966	-0.68	0.22	

In corresponding long series ROCHEFORT 2049:

Table 55: Detected breaks in TX long series

LS code	LS name	Date	Amplitude in °C	MDA in °C	Metadata
2049	ROCHEFORT	no breaks		0.11	

Table 56: Detected breaks in TN long series

LS code	LS name	Date	Amplitude in °C	MDA in °C	Metadata
2049	ROCHEFORT	12/2008	-0.52	0.17	
2049	ROCHEFORT	12/1991	0.60	0.17	
2049	ROCHEFORT	12/1966	-0.45	0.17	

I.2 Extension of the series

I.2.1 Availability since 2015

Year	TN count	TN mean in °C	TX count	TX mean in °C
2015	12	4.52	12	15.54
2016	12	4.40	12	14.91
2017	12	4.01	12	15.47
2018	12	4.23	12	16.43
2019	2	-1.40	2	8.30
2020	0	–	0	–
2021	2	1.70	2	7.55
2022	12	5.60	12	16.33
2023	12	6.47	12	15.61

I.2.2 New homogenization process

New detected breaks

No new breaks have been detected since 2015.

Merging between historical and corresponding long series

Table 57: Detected breaks in TX merged series

LS code	LS name	Date	Amplitude in °C	MDA in °C	Metadata
217	ROCHEFORT	no breaks		0.11	
217	ROCHEFORT	12/1950	-0.60	0.15	observer change
217	ROCHEFORT	12/1927	-1.24	0.15	
217	ROCHEFORT	12/1919	0.61	0.15	

Table 58: Detected breaks in TN merged series

LS code	LS name	Date	Amplitude in °C	MDA in °C	Metadata
217	ROCHEFORT	12/2008	-0.52	0.17	
217	ROCHEFORT	12/1991	0.60	0.17	
217	ROCHEFORT	12/1966	-0.45	0.17	

Final series

Figure 18: Non-homogenized and homogenized annual minimum and maximum temperatures from 1892 to 2018

J CHIMAY 218

J.1 History and homogenization of the series until 2015

J.1.1 History until 2015

HISTORICAL SERIES

218 - CHIMAY (1910 – 2015)

Reference location – longitude: 4°20' 25", latitude: 49°58' 55", altitude: 318 m.

TT CODE	TT NAME	BEGIN	END	STAT ID	LON	LAT	ALT	ΔR	ΔALT
1705	FORGES	8/1910	12/2015	497	4°20' 25"	49°58' 55"	318	0.0	0

CORRESPONDING LONG SERIES

2060 - CHIMAY (1954 – 2015)

Reference location – longitude: 4°20' 25", latitude: 49°58' 55", altitude: 318 m.

TT CODE	TT NAME	BEGIN	END	STAT ID	LON	LAT	ALT	ΔR	ΔALT
1705	FORGES	1/1954	12/2015	497	4°20' 25"	49°58' 55"	318	0.0	0

J.1.2 Homogeneity breaks detected until 2015

In historical series CHIMAY 218:

Table 59: Detected breaks in TX historical series

LS code	LS name	Date	Amplitude in °C	MDA in °C	Metadata
218	CHIMAY	12/1963	-0.42	0.16	
218	CHIMAY	12/1945	-0.45	0.16	
218	CHIMAY	12/1931	-0.91	0.16	
218	CHIMAY	12/1913	0.94	0.16	

Table 60: Detected breaks in TN historical series

LS code	LS name	Date	Amplitude in °C	MDA in °C	Metadata
218	CHIMAY	12/1947	-0.66	0.17	
218	CHIMAY	12/1927	0.32	0.17	
218	CHIMAY	12/1919	0.58	0.17	

In corresponding long series CHIMAY 2060:

Table 61: Detected breaks in TX long series

LS code	LS name	Date	Amplitude in °C	MDA in °C	Metadata
2060	CHIMAY	12/1963	-0.34	0.13	

Table 62: Detected breaks in TN long series

LS code	LS name	Date	Amplitude in °C	MDA in °C	Metadata
2060	CHIMAY	no breaks		0.17	

J.2 Extension of the series

J.2.1 Availability since 2015

Year	TN count	TN mean in °C	TX count	TX mean in °C
2015	12	5.73	12	13.90
2016	12	5.71	12	13.62
2017	12	5.57	12	13.97
2018	12	5.87	12	14.79
2019	11	5.96	11	15.01
2020	11	5.91	11	15.41
2021	12	5.17	12	13.11
2022	12	6.17	12	15.27
2023	12	6.61	12	14.56

J.2.2 New homogenization process

New detected breaks

No new breaks have been detected since 2015.

Merging between historical and corresponding long series

Table 63: Detected breaks in TX merged series

LS code	LS name	Date	Amplitude in °C	MDA in °C	Metadata
218	CHIMAY	12/1963	-0.34	0.13	
218	CHIMAY	12/1945	-0.45	0.16	
218	CHIMAY	12/1931	-0.91	0.16	
218	CHIMAY	12/1913	0.94	0.16	

Table 64: Detected breaks in TN merged series

LS code	LS name	Date	Amplitude in °C	MDA in °C	Metadata
218	CHIMAY	12/1947	-0.66	0.17	
218	CHIMAY	12/1927	0.32	0.17	
218	CHIMAY	12/1919	0.58	0.17	

Final series

Figure 19: Non-homogenized and homogenized annual minimum and maximum temperatures from 1910 to 2023

K STAVELOT 219

K.1 History and homogenization of the series until 2015

K.1.1 History until 2015

HISTORICAL SERIES

219 - STAVELOT (1890 – 2015)

Reference location – longitude: 5°56' 8", latitude: 50°23' 52", altitude: 320 m.

TT CODE	TT NAME	BEGIN	END	STAT ID	LON	LAT	ALT	ΔR	ΔALT
1508	STAVELOT	1/1890	12/2015	349	5°56' 8"	50°23' 52"	320	0.0	0

CORRESPONDING LONG SERIES

2055 - STAVELOT (1954 – 2015)

Reference location – longitude: 5°56' 8", latitude: 50°23' 52", altitude: 320 m.

TT CODE	TT NAME	BEGIN	END	STAT ID	LON	LAT	ALT	ΔR	ΔALT
1508	STAVELOT	1/1954	12/2015	349	5°56' 8"	50°23' 52"	320	0.0	0

K.1.2 Homogeneity breaks detected until 2015

In historical series STAVELOT 219:

Table 65: Detected breaks in TX historical series

LS code	LS name	Date	Amplitude in °C	MDA in °C	Metadata
219	STAVELOT	12/1959	0.49	0.15	
219	STAVELOT	12/1939	-1.64	0.15	
219	STAVELOT	12/1936	0.76	0.15	
219	STAVELOT	12/1917	-0.36	0.15	
219	STAVELOT	12/1908	-0.23	0.15	

Table 66: Detected breaks in TN historical series

LS code	LS name	Date	Amplitude in °C	MDA in °C	Metadata
219	STAVELOT	12/1984	-0.66	0.20	relocation
219	STAVELOT	12/1965	0.51	0.20	
219	STAVELOT	12/1959	0.55	0.20	
219	STAVELOT	12/1938	-0.32	0.20	
219	STAVELOT	12/1919	-0.39	0.20	

In corresponding long series STAVELOT 2055:

Table 67: Detected breaks in TX long series

LS code	LS name	Date	Amplitude in °C	MDA in °C	Metadata
2055	STAVELOT	12/1959	0.67	0.13	

Table 68: Detected breaks in TN long series

LS code	LS name	Date	Amplitude in °C	MDA in °C	Metadata
2055	STAVELOT	12/1984	-0.58	0.17	relocation
2055	STAVELOT	12/1965	0.58	0.17	
2055	STAVELOT	12/1959	0.66	0.17	

K.2 Extension of the series

K.2.1 Availability since 2015

Year	TN count	TN mean in °C	TX count	TX mean in °C
2015	12	4.82	12	14.50
2016	12	4.86	12	14.04
2017	12	4.69	12	14.32
2018	12	4.75	12	15.46
2019	12	4.64	12	15.01
2020	12	4.98	12	15.63
2021	12	4.25	12	13.80
2022	12	4.74	12	15.94
2023	12	5.63	12	15.47

K.2.2 New homogenization process

New detected breaks

Table 69: New detected breaks in TN series

LS code	LS name	Date	Amplitude in °C	MDA in °C	Metadata
219	STAVELOT	3/2018	-0.33	0.20	

Merging between historical and corresponding long series

Table 70: Detected breaks in TX merged series

LS code	LS name	Date	Amplitude in °C	MDA in °C	Metadata
219	STAVELOT	12/1959	0.67	0.13	
219	STAVELOT	12/1939	-1.64	0.15	
219	STAVELOT	12/1936	0.76	0.15	
219	STAVELOT	12/1917	-0.36	0.15	
219	STAVELOT	12/1908	-0.23	0.15	

Table 71: Detected breaks in TN merged series

LS code	LS name	Date	Amplitude in °C	MDA in °C	Metadata
219	STAVELOT	3/2018	-0.33	0.20	relocation
219	STAVELOT	12/1984	-0.58	0.17	
219	STAVELOT	12/1965	0.58	0.17	
219	STAVELOT	12/1959	0.66	0.17	
219	STAVELOT	12/1938	-0.32	0.20	
219	STAVELOT	12/1919	-0.39	0.20	

Final series

Figure 20: Non-homogenized and homogenized annual minimum and maximum temperatures from 1890 to 2023

L MAREDSOUS 220

L.1 History and homogenization of the series until 2015

L.1.1 History until 2015

HISTORICAL SERIES

220 - MAREDSOUS (1893 – 2013)

Reference location – longitude: 4°46' 3", latitude: 50°17' 12", altitude: 222 m.

TT CODE	TT NAME	BEGIN	END	STAT ID	LON	LAT	ALT	ΔR	ΔALT
1301	DENEE MAREDSOUS	1/1893	12/1981	268	4°46' 3"	50°17' 12"	222	0.0	0
608	METTET	1/1982	10/1991	288	4°39' 25"	50°19' 13"	238	8.7	16
1311	SAINT-GERARD	12/1991	11/2013	287	4°44' 9"	50°20' 53"	240	7.2	18

CORRESPONDING LONG SERIES

2043 - DENEE-MAREDSOUS (1/1954 – 11/2013)

Reference location – longitude: 4°46' 3", latitude: 50°17' 12", altitude: 222 m.

TT CODE	TT NAME	BEGIN	END	STAT ID	LON	LAT	ALT	ΔR	ΔALT
1301	DENEE MAREDSOUS	1/1954	12/1981	268	4°46' 3"	50°17' 12"	222	0.0	0
608	METTET	1/1982	10/1991	288	4°39' 25"	50°19' 13"	238	8.7	16
1311	SAINT-GERARD	12/1991	11/2013	287	4°44' 9"	50°20' 53"	240	7.2	18

L.1.2 Homogeneity breaks detected until 2015

In historical series MAREDSOUS 220:

Table 72: Detected breaks in TX historical series

LS code	LS name	Date	Amplitude in °C	MDA in °C	Metadata
220	MAREDSOUS	10/1991	-0.42	0.16	station catenation
220	MAREDSOUS	12/1942	-0.57	0.16	
220	MAREDSOUS	12/1923	-0.38	0.16	

Table 73: Detected breaks in TN historical series

LS code	LS name	Date	Amplitude in °C	MDA in °C	Metadata
220	MAREDSOUS	12/1981	-0.25	0.18	station catenation
220	MAREDSOUS	12/1949	0.37	0.18	
220	MAREDSOUS	12/1936	-0.42	0.18	

In corresponding long series DENEE-MAREDSOUS 2043:

Table 74: Detected breaks in TX long series

LS code	LS name	Date	Amplitude in °C	MDA in °C	Metadata
2043	DENEE-MAREDSOUS	10/1991	-0.51	0.09	station catenation
2043	DENEE-MAREDSOUS	12/1966	0.26	0.09	

Table 75: Detected breaks in TN long series

LS code	LS name	Date	Amplitude in °C	MDA in °C	Metadata
2043	DENEE-MAREDSOUS	no breaks		0.12	

L.2 Extension of the series

L.2.1 Availability since 2015

Year	TN count	TN mean in °C	TX count	TX mean in °C
2015	0	–	0	–
2016	0	–	0	–
2017	0	–	0	–
2018	0	–	0	–
2019	0	–	0	–
2020	0	–	0	–
2021	0	–	0	–
2022	0	–	0	–
2023	0	–	0	–

L.2.2 New homogenization process

New detected breaks

No new breaks have been detected since 2015.

Merging between historical and corresponding long series

Table 76: Detected breaks in TX merged series

LS code	LS name	Date	Amplitude in °C	MDA in °C	Metadata
220	MAREDSOUS	10/1991	-0.51	0.09	station catenation
220	MAREDSOUS	12/1966	0.26	0.09	
220	MAREDSOUS	12/1942	-0.57	0.16	
220	MAREDSOUS	12/1923	-0.38	0.16	

Table 77: Detected breaks in TN merged series

LS code	LS name	Date	Amplitude in °C	MDA in °C	Metadata
220	MAREDSOUS	12/1949	0.37	0.18	
220	MAREDSOUS	12/1936	-0.42	0.18	

Final series

Figure 21: Non-homogenized and homogenized annual minimum and maximum temperatures from 1893 to 2013

M GEMBOUX 221

M.1 History and homogenization of the series until 2015

M.1.1 History until 2015

HISTORICAL SERIES

221 - GEMBOUX (1881 – 2015)

Reference location – longitude: 4°39' 35", latitude: 50°33' 40", altitude: 160 m.

TT CODE	TT NAME	BEGIN	END	STAT ID	LON	LAT	ALT	ΔR	ΔALT
1009	GEMBOUX	5/1881	12/1962	1354	4°39' 35"	50°33' 40"	160	0.0	0
1009	ERNAGE- GEMBOUX	1/1963	11/1999	165	4°41' 14"	50°34' 60"	159	3.1	1
1009	ERNAGE AWS	2/2000	12/2015	640	4°41' 27"	50°34' 57"	157	3.2	3

CORRESPONDING LONG SERIES

2023 - GEMBOUX (1954 – 2015)

Reference location – longitude: 4°41' 14", latitude: 50°34' 60", altitude: 159 m.

TT CODE	TT NAME	BEGIN	END	STAT ID	LON	LAT	ALT	ΔR	ΔALT
1009	GEMBOUX	1/1954	12/1962	1354	4°39' 35"	50°33' 40"	160	0.0	0
1009	ERNAGE- GEMBOUX	1/1963	11/1999	165	4°41' 14"	50°34' 60"	159	0.0	0
1009	ERNAGE AWS	2/2000	12/2015	640	4°41' 27"	50°34' 57"	157	0.3	2

M.1.2 Homogeneity breaks detected until 2015

In historical series GEMBOUX 221:

Table 78: Detected breaks in TX historical series

LS code	LS name	Date	Amplitude in °C	MDA in °C	Metadata
221	GEMBOUX	12/2011	-0.28	0.15	station catenation
221	GEMBOUX	12/1962	-0.28	0.15	
221	GEMBOUX	12/1943	-0.77	0.15	
221	GEMBOUX	12/1916	-0.43	0.15	
221	GEMBOUX	12/1895	0.46	0.15	
221	GEMBOUX	12/1890	-0.82	0.15	

Table 79: Detected breaks in TN historical series

LS code	LS name	Date	Amplitude in °C	MDA in °C	Metadata
221	GEMBLOUX	12/1980	-0.27	0.20	
221	GEMBLOUX	12/1943	0.71	0.20	
221	GEMBLOUX	12/1941	-0.98	0.20	
221	GEMBLOUX	12/1915	0.28	0.20	

In corresponding long series GEMBLOUX 2023:

Table 80: Detected breaks in TX long series

LS code	LS name	Date	Amplitude in °C	MDA in °C	Metadata
2023	GEMBLOUX	12/2011	-0.24	0.10	

Table 81: Detected breaks in TN long series

LS code	LS name	Date	Amplitude in °C	MDA in °C	Metadata
2023	GEMBLOUX	12/1980	-0.24	0.17	

M.2 Extension of the series

M.2.1 Availability since 2015

Year	TN count	TN mean in °C	TX count	TX mean in °C
2015	12	6.40	12	14.40
2016	12	6.39	12	14.09
2017	12	6.52	12	14.41
2018	12	6.61	12	15.43
2019	12	6.64	12	14.92
2020	12	7.05	12	15.73
2021	12	6.05	12	13.72
2022	12	6.99	12	15.85
2023	12	7.67	12	15.33

M.2.2 New homogenization process

New detected breaks

No new breaks have been detected since 2015.

Merging between historical and corresponding long series

Table 82: Detected breaks in TX merged series

LS code	LS name	Date	Amplitude in °C	MDA in °C	Metadata
221	GEMBLOUX	12/2011	-0.24	0.10	
221	GEMBLOUX	12/1943	-0.77	0.15	
221	GEMBLOUX	12/1916	-0.43	0.15	
221	GEMBLOUX	12/1895	0.46	0.15	
221	GEMBLOUX	12/1890	-0.82	0.15	

Table 83: Detected breaks in TN merged series

LS code	LS name	Date	Amplitude in °C	MDA in °C	Metadata
221	GEMBLOUX	12/1980	-0.24	0.17	
221	GEMBLOUX	12/1943	0.71	0.20	
221	GEMBLOUX	12/1941	-0.98	0.20	
221	GEMBLOUX	12/1915	0.28	0.20	

Final series

Figure 22: Non-homogenized and homogenized annual minimum and maximum temperatures from 1881 to 2023

N MONT-RIGI 222

N.1 History and homogenization of the series until 2015

N.1.1 History until 2015

HISTORICAL SERIES

222 - MONT-RIGI (1928 – 2015)

Reference location – longitude: 6°3' 40", latitude: 50°31' 7", altitude: 672 m.

TT CODE	TT NAME	BEGIN	END	STAT ID	LON	LAT	ALT	ΔR	ΔALT
1600	BARAQUE MICHEL	1/1928	11/1953	1353	6°3' 40"	50°31' 7"	672	0.0	0
1600	MONT-RIGI	12/1953	12/1953	359	6°3' 53"	50°30' 53"	673	0.5	1
1505	BOTRANGE	1/1954	11/1984	345	6°5' 43"	50°30' 0"	692	3.2	20
1510	BOTRANGEPARC	1/1985	7/1989	343	6°6' 1"	50°29' 54"	655	3.6	17
1600	MONT-RIGI	11/1989	6/2003	359	6°3' 53"	50°30' 53"	673	0.5	1
1600	MONT RIGI AWS	7/2003	12/2015	626	6°4' 29"	50°30' 42"	673	1.2	1

CORRESPONDING LONG SERIES

2053 - MONT-RIGI (1954 – 2015)

Reference location – longitude: 6°5' 43", latitude: 50°30' 0", altitude: 692 m.

TT CODE	TT NAME	BEGIN	END	STAT ID	LON	LAT	ALT	ΔR	ΔALT
1505	BOTRANGE	1/1954	11/1984	345	6°5' 43"	50°30' 0"	692	0.0	0
1510	BOTRANGEPARC	1/1985	7/1989	343	6°6' 1"	50°29' 54"	655	0.4	37
1600	MONT-RIGI	11/1989	6/2003	359	6°3' 53"	50°30' 53"	673	2.7	19
1600	MONT RIGI AWS	7/2003	12/2015	626	6°4' 29"	50°30' 42"	673	2.0	19

N.1.2 Homogeneity breaks detected until 2015

In historical series MONT-RIGI 222:

Table 84: Detected breaks in TX historical series

LS code	LS name	Date	Amplitude in °C	MDA in °C	Metadata
222	MONT-RIGI	7/1989	0.20	0.15	station catenation
222	MONT-RIGI	11/1984	0.73	0.15	station catenation
222	MONT-RIGI	12/1977	-0.45	0.15	
222	MONT-RIGI	11/1953	-1.23	0.15	station catenation
222	MONT-RIGI	12/1935	0.49	0.15	

Table 85: Detected breaks in TN historical series

LS code	LS name	Date	Amplitude in °C	MDA in °C	Metadata
222	MONT-RIGI	12/1937	-0.33	0.17	

In corresponding long series MONT-RIGI 2053:

Table 86: Detected breaks in TX long series

LS code	LS name	Date	Amplitude in °C	MDA in °C	Metadata
2053	MONT-RIGI	7/1989	0.57	0.16	station catenation
2053	MONT-RIGI	11/1984	0.52	0.16	station catenation
2053	MONT-RIGI	12/1977	-0.38	0.16	

Table 87: Detected breaks in TN long series

LS code	LS name	Date	Amplitude in °C	MDA in °C	Metadata
2053	MONT-RIGI	12/1960	-0.19	0.12	

N.2 Extension of the series

N.2.1 Availability since 2015

Year	TN count	TN mean in °C	TX count	TX mean in °C
2015	12	4.12	12	11.11
2016	12	4.17	12	10.72
2017	12	4.17	12	11.03
2018	12	4.56	12	12.21
2019	12	4.49	12	11.68
2020	12	4.67	12	12.15
2021	12	3.78	12	10.46
2022	12	4.80	12	12.49
2023	12	4.92	12	11.91

N.2.2 New homogenization process

New detected breaks

Table 88: New detected breaks in TX series

LS code	LS name	Date	Amplitude in °C	MDA in °C	Metadata
222	MONT-RIGI	11/2014	-0.45	0.12	

Merging between historical and corresponding long series

Table 89: Detected breaks in TX merged series

LS code	LS name	Date	Amplitude in °C	MDA in °C	Metadata
222	MONT-RIGI	11/2014	-0.45	0.12	
222	MONT-RIGI	7/1989	0.57	0.16	station catenation
222	MONT-RIGI	11/1984	0.52	0.16	station catenation
222	MONT-RIGI	12/1977	-0.38	0.16	
222	MONT-RIGI	11/1953	-1.23	0.15	station catenation
222	MONT-RIGI	12/1935	0.49	0.15	

Table 90: Detected breaks in TN merged series

LS code	LS name	Date	Amplitude in °C	MDA in °C	Metadata
222	MONT-RIGI	12/1960	-0.19	0.12	
222	MONT-RIGI	12/1937	-0.33	0.17	

Final series

Figure 23: Non-homogenized and homogenized annual minimum and maximum temperatures from 1928 to 2023

O THIMISTER 223

O.1 History and homogenization of the series until 2015

O.1.1 History until 2015

HISTORICAL SERIES

223 - THIMISTER (1881 – 2015)

Reference location – longitude: 5°51' 48", latitude: 50°39' 15", altitude: 280 m.

TT CODE	TT NAME	BEGIN	END	STAT ID	LON	LAT	ALT	ΔR	ΔALT
1501	VERVIERS	1/1881	12/1899	1355	5°53' 1"	50°35' 48"	255	6.6	25
1500	THIMISTER	1/1900	12/2004	333	5°51' 48"	50°39' 15"	280	0.0	0
1504	WALHORN	1/2005	12/2015	337	6°2' 5"	50°41' 53"	220	13.1	60

CORRESPONDING LONG SERIES

2051 - THIMISTER (1954 – 2015)

Reference location – longitude: 5°51' 48", latitude: 50°39' 15", altitude: 280 m.

TT CODE	TT NAME	BEGIN	END	STAT ID	LON	LAT	ALT	ΔR	ΔALT
1500	THIMISTER	1/1954	12/2004	333	5°51' 48"	50°39' 15"	280	0.0	0
1504	WALHORN	1/2005	12/2015	337	6°2' 5"	50°41' 53"	220	13.1	60

O.1.2 Homogeneity breaks detected until 2015

In historical series **THIMISTER 223**:

Table 91: Detected breaks in TX historical series

LS code	LS name	Date	Amplitude in °C	MDA in °C	Metadata
223	THIMISTER	12/2004	0.61	0.19	station catenation relocation
223	THIMISTER	3/1989	-0.56	0.19	
223	THIMISTER	12/1975	0.27	0.19	
223	THIMISTER	12/1956	-0.64	0.19	
223	THIMISTER	12/1947	-0.68	0.19	
223	THIMISTER	12/1936	-0.79	0.19	
223	THIMISTER	12/1932	-0.71	0.19	
223	THIMISTER	12/1927	0.28	0.19	
223	THIMISTER	12/1923	1.57	0.19	

Table 92: Detected breaks in TN historical series

LS code	LS name	Date	Amplitude in °C	MDA in °C	Metadata
223	THIMISTER	12/2004	-0.68	0.22	station catenation
223	THIMISTER	12/1971	-0.80	0.22	
223	THIMISTER	12/1968	0.59	0.22	
223	THIMISTER	12/1945	0.35	0.22	
223	THIMISTER	12/1934	0.58	0.22	
223	THIMISTER	12/1921	-1.01	0.22	
223	THIMISTER	12/1899	0.48	0.22	

In corresponding long series THIMISTER 2051:

Table 93: Detected breaks in TX long series

LS code	LS name	Date	Amplitude in °C	MDA in °C	Metadata
2051	THIMISTER	12/2004	0.55	0.12	station catenation relocation
2051	THIMISTER	3/1989	-0.58	0.12	
2051	THIMISTER	12/1975	0.37	0.12	
2051	THIMISTER	12/1956	-0.46	0.12	

Table 94: Detected breaks in TN long series

LS code	LS name	Date	Amplitude in °C	MDA in °C	Metadata
2051	THIMISTER	12/2004	-0.66	0.19	station catenation
2051	THIMISTER	12/1971	-0.64	0.19	
2051	THIMISTER	12/1968	0.66	0.19	

0.2 Extension of the series

0.2.1 Availability since 2015

Year	TN count	TN mean in °C	TX count	TX mean in °C
2015	12	5.87	12	14.99
2016	12	5.82	12	14.57
2017	12	5.90	12	14.85
2018	12	6.03	12	16.18
2019	11	6.24	11	15.99
2020	12	6.19	12	16.28
2021	11	6.05	11	14.45
2022	12	6.36	12	16.37
2023	3	2.17	3	8.27

O.2.2 New homogenization process

New detected breaks

Table 95: New detected breaks in TX series

LS code	LS name	Date	Amplitude in °C	MDA in °C	Metadata
223	THIMISTER	11/2013	0.38	0.14	

Merging between historical and corresponding long series

Table 96: Detected breaks in TX merged series

LS code	LS name	Date	Amplitude in °C	MDA in °C	Metadata
223	THIMISTER	11/2013	0.38	0.14	station catenation relocation
223	THIMISTER	12/2004	0.55	0.12	
223	THIMISTER	3/1989	-0.58	0.12	
223	THIMISTER	12/1975	0.37	0.12	
223	THIMISTER	12/1956	-0.46	0.12	
223	THIMISTER	12/1947	-0.68	0.19	
223	THIMISTER	12/1936	-0.79	0.19	
223	THIMISTER	12/1932	-0.71	0.19	
223	THIMISTER	12/1927	0.28	0.19	
223	THIMISTER	12/1923	1.57	0.19	

Table 97: Detected breaks in TN merged series

LS code	LS name	Date	Amplitude in °C	MDA in °C	Metadata
223	THIMISTER	12/2004	-0.66	0.19	station catenation
223	THIMISTER	12/1971	-0.64	0.19	
223	THIMISTER	12/1968	0.66	0.19	
223	THIMISTER	12/1945	0.35	0.22	
223	THIMISTER	12/1934	0.58	0.22	
223	THIMISTER	12/1921	-1.01	0.22	
223	THIMISTER	12/1899	0.48	0.22	station catenation

Final series

Figure 24: Non-homogenized and homogenized annual minimum and maximum temperatures from 1881 to 2023

P UCCLE 224

P.1 History and homogenization of the series until 2015

P.1.1 History until 2015

HISTORICAL SERIES

224 - UCCLE (1880 – 2015)

Reference location – longitude: 4°21' 33", latitude: 50°47' 51", altitude: 100 m.

TT CODE	TT NAME	BEGIN	END	STAT ID	LON	LAT	ALT	ΔR	ΔALT
1065	Saint-Josse-ten-Noode	1/1880	6/1886	1366	4°22' 8"	50°51' 7"	51	6.1	49
905	UCCLE-UKKEL (OU-VERT)	7/1886	6/1983	166	4°21' 25"	50°47' 51"	100	0.2	0
904	UCCLE-UKKEL (FERME)	6/1983	12/2015	169	4°21' 33"	50°47' 51"	100	0.0	0

CORRESPONDING LONG SERIES

2032 - UCCLE (1954 – 2015)

Reference location – longitude: 4°21' 33", latitude: 50°47' 51", altitude: 100 m.

TT CODE	TT NAME	BEGIN	END	STAT ID	LON	LAT	ALT	ΔR	ΔALT
905	UCCLE-UKKEL (OU-VERT)	1/1954	6/1983	166	4°21' 25"	50°47' 51"	100	0.2	0
904	UCCLE-UKKEL (FERME)	6/1983	12/2015	169	4°21' 33"	50°47' 51"	100	0.0	0

P.1.2 Homogeneity breaks detected until 2015

In historical series UCCLE 224:

Table 98: Detected breaks in TX historical series

LS code	LS name	Date	Amplitude in °C	MDA in °C	Metadata
224	UCCLE	6/1983	-0.91	0.15	station catenation
224	UCCLE	12/1899	0.51	0.15	
224	UCCLE	12/1890	-0.51	0.15	

Table 99: Detected breaks in TN historical series

LS code	LS name	Date	Amplitude in °C	MDA in °C	Metadata
224	UCCLE	6/1983	0.15	0.17	station catenation
224	UCCLE	6/1886	-0.59	0.17	station catenation

In corresponding long series UCCLE 2032:

Table 100: Detected breaks in TX long series

LS code	LS name	Date	Amplitude in °C	MDA in °C	Metadata
2032	UCCLE	6/1983	-0.84	0.10	station catenation

Table 101: Detected breaks in TN long series

LS code	LS name	Date	Amplitude in °C	MDA in °C	Metadata
2032	UCCLE	6/1983	0.09	0.15	station catenation

P.2 Extension of the series

P.2.1 Availability since 2015

Year	TN count	TN mean in °C	TX count	TX mean in °C
2015	12	7.44	12	15.25
2016	12	7.38	12	14.75
2017	12	7.55	12	15.23
2018	12	7.87	12	16.12
2019	12	7.67	12	15.73
2020	12	8.05	12	16.42
2021	12	7.04	12	14.58
2022	12	7.98	12	16.46
2023	12	8.43	12	15.90

P.2.2 New homogenization process

New detected breaks

No new breaks have been detected since 2015.

Merging between historical and corresponding long series

The merging is generally performed using the homogenized long series for the period where it is available with the homogenized historical series for the period preceding the start of the long series. This approach is followed for all series except when the metadata clearly supports the choice of the corrections applied in the historical series against those used in the long series. For UCCLE, the break detected in 1963 in the long series is not supported by metadata. In the corresponding historical series, this break is not present but a break of similar amplitude is detected in 1983. The origin of this break in 1983 is clearly identified as the move from closed to open shelter. We suspect that the break in 1963 is erroneous. Therefore, it was ultimately decided to use the historical series for the whole period 1880-2015.

Table 102: Detected breaks in TX merged series

LS code	LS name	Date	Amplitude in °C	MDA in °C	Metadata
224	UCCLE	6/1983	-0.91	0.15	station catenation
224	UCCLE	12/1899	0.51	0.15	
224	UCCLE	12/1890	-0.51	0.15	

Table 103: Detected breaks in TN merged series

LS code	LS name	Date	Amplitude in °C	MDA in °C	Metadata
224	UCCLE	6/1983	0.15	0.17	station catenation
224	UCCLE	6/1886	-0.59	0.17	station catenation

Final series

Figure 25: Non-homogenized and homogenized annual minimum and maximum temperatures from 1880 to 2023

Q Comments on the historical series and their homogenization

CODE	NAME	COMMENTS
201	DEURNE	Observations by Skeyes at Antwerp Airport. Series not extended beyond 2021 due to quality issues. For the TN series, the homogenization results in the historical (HS) and long series (LS) are not consistent. In the HS series (Code 201), breaks are identified in 1997 and 2002 while no breaks are identified in the corresponding LS series (Code 2002). The data are coming from the same station which means that any break should be present in both series. Running the new homogenization process lets appear two additional breaks in the LS series in 1994 and 2002. The position of the first break in 1994, instead of 1997 in the HS series, has been validated.
203	ZAVENTEM	Observations by Skeyes at Zaventem Airport. Series starts in Saint-Josse in 1989 and is extended with Zaventem observations since 1954. Name of the series has been changed from BRUXELLES-ZAVENTEM to ZAVENTEM.
206	EZEMAAL	Station Ezemaal closed on 31-05-2017. Possible extension with Ransberg station (Code 1110 in Table TEMPERATURE).
208	JALHAY	Shelter replaced on 26-10-2023. Too close to the end of the series for identifying and correcting possible break.
210	LEUVEN	For TX, the homogenized historical series has not been produced during the previous homogenization phase. The quality of the data before 1954 was considered as insufficient. Only the homogenized long series starting in 1954 is available.
212	OOSTENDE	Observations by Skeyes at Oostende Airport. As for several stations operated by Skeyes, there have been quality issues for several years. Based on Homer quality control, quality issues seem to start around 2016-2017. Defective connection between PT100 and ADAM module causes too low temperatures. According to Skeyes, this issue started in October 2021. Change of sensor used for temperature on 5/12/2023 from PT100 to Vaisala HumiCap. Conclusion : erroneous or at least suspicious data from oct. 2021 to dec. 2023
213	SINT-TRUIDEN	The station is located in GORSEM since 1954 (Proefcentrum Fruiteelt). Possible unreported location change in 2008 with move Fruiteelt Profcentrum from Gorsem to Kerkom.
216	LEOPOLDSBURG	Stevenson shelter replaced on 23-03-2022 but no break detected by Homer.
217	ROCHEFORT	Long interruption between 03-2019 to 09-2021. Extended to 12-2018. Data OK since 09-2021. Need to bridge the gap.
218	CHIMAY	Same station on the Abbey site since the start of the series in 1910. Stevenson shelter replaced on 23-11-2023. Too close to the end of the series for identifying and correcting possible break.
219	STAVELOT	Same station since the start of the series in 1890. Quality is probably decreasing in recent years. Stevenson shelter replaced on 26-10-2023. Too close to the end of the series for identifying and correcting possible break.
220	MAREDSOUS	Station (SAINT-GERARD) closed on 30-11-2013.
221	GEMBLOUX	RMI AWS station.

222	MONT-RIGI	RMI AWS station. Break detected in 2014 in TX series. Origin under investigation.
223	THIMISTER	Missing data in 2019 (10 %) and 2021 (10 %). Quality is probably decreasing in recent years.
224	UCCLE	Manual observations from closed shelter in climatological parc. Measurements differ from those observed in the AWS station located in the synoptic parc. The latter are currently considered as the reference observations for Uccle. For UCCLE, a break was detected in 1963 in the long series but it is not supported by metadata. In the corresponding historical series, this break is not present but a break of similar amplitude is detected in 1983. The origin of this break in 1983 is clearly identified as the move from closed to open shelter. We suspect that the break in 1963 in the long series is erroneous. Therefore, it was ultimately decided to use the historical series for the whole period 1880-2015.

R Linear trends 1981-2023

Table 105: Linear trend (S) and p-values (P) over the 1981-2023 period for the non-homogenized (RA) and homogenized (HO) TN, TX and TM series. The slopes are expressed in °C/10-year

CODE	NAME	TN S RA	TN P RA	TN S HO	TN P HO	TX S RA	TX P RA	TX S HO	TX P HO	TM S RA	TM P RA	TM S HO	TM P HO
212	OOSTENDE	0.19	0.017484	0.32	0.000445	0.39	0.000023	0.50	0.000001	0.29	0.000446	0.41	0.000014
201	DEURNE	0.36	0.000027	0.35	0.000128	0.52	0.000001	0.55	0.000002	0.44	0.000001	0.45	0.000005
216	LEOPOLDSBURG	0.37	0.000033	0.38	0.000021	0.62	0.000000	0.58	0.000000	0.50	0.000000	0.48	0.000000
206	EZEMAAL	0.41	0.000276	0.34	0.002513	0.47	0.000113	0.55	0.000047	0.44	0.000051	0.45	0.000117
213	SINT-TRUIDEN	0.36	0.000073	0.30	0.000923	0.33	0.001424	0.58	0.000000	0.35	0.000163	0.44	0.000003
210	LEUVEN	0.38	0.000032	0.39	0.000010	0.46	0.000017	0.62	0.000000	0.42	0.000007	0.50	0.000000
203	ZAVENSTEM	0.27	0.001440	0.36	0.000033	0.49	0.000004	0.56	0.000000	0.38	0.000033	0.46	0.000001
221	GEMBLOUX	0.42	0.000002	0.41	0.000003	0.48	0.000008	0.53	0.000000	0.45	0.000002	0.47	0.000000
224	UCCLE	0.36	0.000017	0.35	0.000031	0.47	0.000009	0.54	0.000000	0.41	0.000006	0.44	0.000001
220	MAREDSOUS	0.25	0.051757	0.23	0.070333	0.34	0.017327	0.48	0.001154	0.30	0.022524	0.35	0.006915
217	ROCHEFORT	0.41	0.000681	0.32	0.004596	0.58	0.000001	0.57	0.000007	0.49	0.000004	0.44	0.000041
223	THIMISTER	0.10	0.236736	0.35	0.000026	0.72	0.000000	0.56	0.000001	0.41	0.000043	0.45	0.000001
208	JALHAY	0.65	0.000000	0.39	0.000008	0.72	0.000000	0.60	0.000000	0.68	0.000000	0.49	0.000000
219	STAVELOT	0.20	0.010319	0.37	0.000014	0.54	0.000001	0.57	0.000000	0.37	0.000010	0.47	0.000000
218	CHIMAY	0.31	0.000529	0.31	0.000104	0.55	0.000002	0.58	0.000000	0.43	0.000014	0.45	0.000001
222	MONT-RIGI	0.35	0.000229	0.32	0.000218	0.59	0.000001	0.51	0.000002	0.47	0.000006	0.42	0.000010